

BULETINUL INSTITUTULUI POLITEHNIC DIN IAȘI
Publicat de
Universitatea Tehnică „Gheorghe Asachi” din Iași
Volumul 68 (72), Numărul 1, 2022
Secția
CHIMIE și INGINERIE CHIMICĂ

SCREENING OF THE AMINO ACID-BASED SOLVENTS FOR CARBON DIOXIDE ABSORPTION

BY

RAMONA ELENA TĂTARU-FĂRMUȘ¹, NICOLAE APOSTOLESCU¹,
CORINA CERNĂTESCU¹, CLAUDIA COBZARU¹ and MIHAELA POROCH^{2,*}

¹“Gheorghe Asachi” Technical University of Iași, “Cristofor Simionescu” Faculty of Chemical Engineering and Environmental Protection, Iași, Romania

²“Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy Iași, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Preventive Medicine and Interdisciplinarity, Iași, Romania

Received: January 10, 2022

Accepted for publication: February 25, 2022

Abstract. Post-combustion separation and capture of CO₂ from flue gases resulting from the burning of fossil fuels is a challenging technique due to the low pressure and low concentration of carbon dioxide, the impurities in the flue gases and the cost of regenerating the absorber. Researchers have developed various CO₂ capture technologies such as absorption, adsorption, and membrane separation cryogenic technology. Of these, absorption was the most widely used. A wide variety of organic and inorganic substances have been proposed as solvents for CO₂ uptake. But, these solvents have some major disadvantage such as: low absorption rate for K₂CO₃ solutions, high energy consumption for the amine solutions, high volatility and toxicity of ammonia. These can be solved by using another selective solvent for carbon dioxide. This paper provides information available in the literature on current solvents and the potential for amino acid salts to be used as absorbent for CO₂ capture.

Keywords: acid gas, chemisorption, energy efficiency, equimolar blend, greenhouse gases.

*Corresponding author; *e-mail*: boanca.mihaela@umfiiasi.ro

1. Introduction

The industrial revolution meant increasing mankind's dependence on fossil fuels. The main elements of fossil fuels are carbon and hydrogen. Through the process of burning fuels, the heat mainly used for energy is released. The amount of carbon dioxide in the gas phase depends on the carbon content of the fuel. Over time, it has been observed that the Earth's temperature depends directly on the concentration of CO₂, and an increase in global average temperature has been recorded since the early 1900s. An increase of a few degrees Celsius is expected to significantly affect the climate. As a result, there is an urgent need to address the issue of high CO₂ emissions.

Carbon capture and sequestration (CCS) is the only technology available method that can reduce the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere due to the burning of fossil fuels (Ayoub *et al.*, 2018; Paul and Thomsen, 2012; Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Sang Sefidi and Luis, 2019; Thee, 2013; Zhang, 2021). CCS is a technology that can only be used only for stationary sources, which are responsible for 50% of total emissions (de Coninck *et al.*, 2018; Edenhofer *et al.*, 2011; Hoegh-Guldberg *et al.*, 2018; Tschakert *et al.*, 2018). But like any new technology, CCS cannot be widely applied due to its direct cost constraints. In addition, there are not enough data on the long-term health effect of this process for humanity. Carbon dioxide capture can be achieved by several methods, some tested on an industrial scale, some on pilot scale, and others under development and evaluation. The choice of a technology for a particular method of capturing carbon dioxide depends on many factors, such as: the partial pressure of CO₂ in the gas flow; the required recovering degree of CO₂; sensitivity to impurities; desired purity of carbon dioxide; process operating costs and the cost of additives needed to overcome dirt and corrosion; environmental impact etc. Chemical absorption systems seem to be the best short-term option for capturing CO₂ from gaseous streams (Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

2. Conventional solvents for carbon dioxide capture by absorption

The process of chemical absorption involves the reaction of carbon dioxide with a chemical solvent, resulting an intermediate compound. This intermediate can be decomposed by heating, producing the original solvent and a CO₂ stream that is directed to other technologies (Lawal *et al.*, 2011; Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In absorption processes, a CO₂-containing waste gas stream enters the bottom of an absorber. The solvent enters the top of the absorber and comes into contact with the gas (counter current flow). Thus, CO₂ is removed and the treated gas exits through the top of the column. CO₂ is absorbed and the CO₂-enriched solvent exits at the bottom of the absorber (Fig. 1).

The selectivity of this separation process is relatively high and there is a possibility of obtaining a relatively pure CO₂ flux. Although feasibility studies

show that it will remain competitive in the future, this technology has many problems, depending on the solvent chosen for separation: high cost, toxicity, degradation and solvent evaporation, low absorption rate etc. (Ayoub *et al.*, 2018; Lawal *et al.*, 2011; Leung *et al.*, 2014; Mondal *et al.*, 2012; Thee, 2013).

Solvent selection plays an important role in the success of the CO₂ absorption process because the performance of the CO₂ separation process depends on the behaviour of the solvent. A number of factors must be considered when choosing an absorbent solution: the solubility of the gaseous component in the liquid phase, the reactive properties of the gas and the absorbent (Lawal *et al.*, 2011; SINTEF, 2009). CO₂ is considered an acid gas because, when it is absorbed by a water-based solvent, an acid solution will form. Thus, an alkaline absorbent is desirable for the absorption of acid gas. Alkaline solutions allow the neutralization of any acid formed by the absorption of gas, thus increasing the amount of gas that can be absorbed for a certain volume of liquid solvent.

Fig. 1 – Schematic of a basic chemical absorption process for CO₂ capture.

The process of chemical absorption of carbon dioxide is applied in several variants:

- ⇒ absorption in potassium carbonate solutions;
- ⇒ absorption in amine solution;
- ⇒ absorption in aqueous ammonia solutions;
- ⇒ absorption in ionic liquids.

Potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) has been chosen as a system to be used in high pressure CO₂ capture applications and is the main method practically used. Aqueous potassium carbonate is a good solvent for capturing carbon dioxide due to its low regenerative energy, low degradation and low corrosivity (Borhani *et*

et al., 2015; Ramazani *et al.*, 2016; Shen *et al.*, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2017). The main challenge of the CO₂ absorption system in potassium carbonate solutions is the slow reaction rate compared to the amine solution absorption system, especially in post-combustion conditions: low temperature and low CO₂ partial pressure (Grimekis *et al.*, 2019; Harja *et al.*, 2021; Hu *et al.*, 2017b; Li *et al.*, 2019; Skurygin and Poroyko, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2017). The activation of K₂CO₃ solutions appears to be an effective way to improve this solvent performance (Devries, 2014; Grimekis *et al.*, 2019; Harja *et al.*, 2021; Hu *et al.*, 2016).

The absorption in amine solutions has been used in natural gas industry in the last decades to remove CO₂ (Godin *et al.*, 2021; Tataru -Farmus *et al.*, 2007). Monoethanol amine (MEA) is the most widely used solvent, due to both its fast absorption rate and its low cost (Lang *et al.*, 2017; Leung *et al.*, 2014). However, MEA and others amines have some disadvantages, such as: high energy loss for solvent regeneration (over 80 % of the total energy consumption), high degradation rate and corrosivity in presence of O₂ (Godin *et al.*, 2021; Wu *et al.*, 2020). Another problem that must be addressed when using amines as a solvent for carbon dioxide is related to their toxicity. A solvent with high toxicity is not the best choice because it involves environmental issues (Koronaki *et al.*, 2015; Lang *et al.*, 2017).

The process of absorbing carbon dioxide from flue gases into ammonia solutions has been reported to be very effective (Kozak *et al.*, 2009; Molina and Bouallou, 2015, 2017; Rivera-Tinoco and Bouallou, 2010; Yeh *et al.*, 2005). The advantages of this technology are lower regeneration energy consumption and fertilizer production. However, the problem of ammonia loss is the main obstacle to the widespread application of ammonia absorption technology. Due to the volatile nature of ammonia, it is necessary to cool the flue gases and to reduce its ammonia volatilization. As a result, this process involves high energy consumption and costs (Jilvero *et al.*, 2014; Liu *et al.*, 2009; Molina and Bouallou, 2015; Valenti and Bonalumi, 2018).

As a result of the requirements for more environmentally friendly, but also more sustainable techniques, a category of solvent has developed: ionic liquids (IL). IL could be classified into two main groups: conventional and functionalized. CO₂ is absorbed in the conventional IL by the means of a physical process, at low capacity and selectivity, while the structure of functionalized IL is modified to permit a chemisorption of CO₂ at high capacity, rate and selectivity (Farsi and Soroush, 2020). The advantages of carbon dioxide capture technology in ionic liquids are due to its remarkable properties, such as: negligible volatility, high thermal stability, non-flammability, solvation and high solubility of CO₂ (Aghaie *et al.*, 2018; Bai *et al.*, 2017; Hasib-ur-Rahman *et al.*, 2010; Ramdin *et al.*, 2012; Sánchez, 2008; Wappel *et al.*, 2010; Zhang *et al.*, 2016). The number of ILs that can be used as absorption solvents is very large; the imidazolium class is most widely investigated and reported in the literature (Janiczek *et al.*, 2012). However, the use of ionic liquids as solvents for carbon dioxide presents 2 major

challenges: high viscosity and high production price (Aghaie *et al.*, 2018; Brennecke and Gurkan, 2010; Zareie-kordshouli *et al.*, 2016; Wu *et al.*, 2020).

A special category of absorbents are solvent blends. These mixtures are usually composed of two individual solvents of different compositions. The advantage of mixed solvents would be that they can extract favourable performance from the initial solutions, eliminating the disadvantages. In the literature there are studies on blends based on potassium carbonate – amines (Behr *et al.*, 2011; Cullinane and Rochelle, 2006; Devries, 2014; Harja *et al.*, 2021; Ramezani *et al.*, 2018; Tang *et al.*, 2011; Thee, 2013), potassium carbonate - ionic liquids (Ochedi *et al.*, 2020; Sistla and Khanna, 2015), mixtures of amines (Adeosun and Abu-Zahra, 2013; Ansaloni *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2016; Du *et al.*, 2016; Luo *et al.*, 2017; Nwaoha *et al.*, 2018; Pacheco *et al.*, 2000; Perinu *et al.*, 2017), amines and ionic liquids (Haider *et al.*, 2016; Xiao *et al.*, 2019; Wu *et al.*, 2020).

Recent literature concludes that the solvents developed so far have many disadvantages and there is a need for research and development of new technologies and new solvents for carbon capture.

3. Amino acid salt (AAS) as CO₂ absorption solvent

Because the amine group is the main reason for the use of amines as a solvent for CO₂ separation, specialized studies have focused on other types of solvents with this functional group, but have better properties than amines (Holst *et al.*, 2009; Sanchez-Fernandez *et al.*, 2013; Sang Sefidi and Luis, 2019; Song *et al.*, 2012). Amino acids are amphiprotic species, organic compounds that contain one or more amino groups (—NH₂) and one or more carboxyl groups (—COOH). CO₂ absorption using amino acid-based solvents is a bio-mimetic treatment of the CO₂ capture process, due to its resemblance to the binding of CO₂ in blood by proteins, such as hemoglobin (Lerche *et al.*, 2009). According to the nature of the radical on which the two functional groups are grafted, amino acids can be aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic (Table 1).

In water, amino acids form a zwitterion. Based on the reaction mechanism of CO₂ and amino acids, the basic (alkaline) species is the active form. Therefore, amino acids must be deprotonated to react with CO₂ at neutral pH. Deprotonation of amino acids is achieved by adding an equimolar amount from a strong base (Ayoub *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2019; Paul and Thomsen, 2012; Shen *et al.*, 2015; Thee *et al.*, 2014; Zarei *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Some of the bases considered to neutralize amino acids are KOH, NaOH and LiOH. Research has suggested that deprotonated amino acids with potassium hydroxide are more reactive than those deprotonated with sodium hydroxide (Holst *et al.*, 2012; Lim *et al.*, 2012; Zarei *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Majchrowicz (Majchrowicz, 2014) showed that the reactivity of the potassium salt of L-prolinate was higher than that of its sodium salt in reaction with CO₂.

Deprotonation of amino acids can also be achieved with amine solutions. Literature reports the use of monoethanolamine MEA and methylamino-propylamine MAPA solutions for this stage of neutralization. In the case of neutralization with MEA, the amine group of the amino acid is the active agent for CO₂ capture, and the amine group of the MEA acts as a counterion to deprotonate the amino acids. The results are better for CO₂ absorption in the amine-amino acid salts than absorption in acid salts of an inorganic base, like KOH (Ciftja *et al.*, 2014; Knuutila *et al.*, 2011).

Table 1
Classification and structure of some amino acids

aliphatic	aromatic	heterocyclic
Alanine $C_3H_7NO_2$ 		
Cysteine $C_3H_7NO_2S$ 		
Asparagine $C_4H_8N_2O_3$ 		

Regarding the absorption of CO₂ in different amino acid salt solutions, Table 2 lists some of the experimental studies. Thus, the most commonly used amino acids are taurine, alanine, sarcosine and proline as potassium or sodium salts.

Table 2
Amino Acid Salts used in experimental studies

Compound	AAS solutions	Reference
Arginine	Potassium salt	(Holst <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Glycine	Potassium salt	(Bao <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Hallenbeck <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Li and Rochelle, 2011; Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	MEA / AMP	(Ciftja <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Taurine	Potassium salt	(Hallenbeck <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Li and Rochelle, 2011; Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	Sodium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	Lithium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	MEA/AMP	(Ciftja <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Alanine	Potassium salt	(Holst <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Li and Rochelle, 2011; Lim <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	Sodium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	Lithium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	MEA/ AMP	(Ciftja <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Aminobutyric acid	Potassium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	Sodium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	Lithium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
Methyl alanine	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Serine	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	MEA/AMP	(Ciftja <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Cysteine	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Proline	Potassium salt	(Hallenbeck <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Lim <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Paul and Thomsen, 2012; Shen <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
	MEA / AMP	(Ciftja <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Pyroglutamic acid	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Asparagine	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Glutamine	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Zarei <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Diglycine	Potassium salt	(Song <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
Lysine	Potassium salt	(Hallenbeck <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Shen <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
6-aminohexanoic acid	Potassium salt	(Holst <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	Sodium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
	Lithium salt	(Majchrowicz <i>et al.</i> , 2006)
Glutamic acid	Potassium salt	(Holst <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
Methionine	Potassium salt	(Holst <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
Sarcosine	Potassium salt	(Holst <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Knuutila <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Li and Rochelle, 2011)
	Sodium salt	(Li and Rochelle, 2011)

Additionally, in the experimental studies, the absorption performance of amino acid salts is compared to MEA as the most important conventional amine and the authors claimed that the solutions of the amino acid salt can be considered as an attractive solvent. Lysine, proline, glycine, alanine and sarcosine are reported as having a good reaction constant with carbon dioxide, larger than that of amines. Some of the AAs properties like ionic strength, large CO₂ solubility, high surface tension and the cation used are shown to be important factors influencing the reactivity of amino acids (Ramezani *et al.*, 2020).

Although amino acids are more expensive than amines, they have advantages due to their physical and chemical properties: low volatility, low toxicity and resistance to degradation. For these reasons and because they are not harmful for the human health, amino acids can be selected for carbon dioxide absorption. Nevertheless, the main disadvantages of amino acid salts are: solvent corrosive nature and high energy needed for regeneration. Amino acid salts precipitate at high concentrations or high CO₂ loading during CO₂ absorption which causes damage to absorption plant and also reduces mass transfer (Ramezani *et al.*, 2020).

In the latest years, different blends of AASs and other liquids to form a new absorbent mixture has gained attentions (Ahmed and Wiheeb, 2020; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Hu *et al.*, 2018; Kasturi *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2019; Thee *et al.*, 2014). The role of AAS in a blended solution is to enhance the absorption or the desorption performance. The results showed a great potential to apply the blended solution in industry. Proline and sarcosine have better promoting effects compared to MEA in alkaline solution solvents (Aronu *et al.*, 2011; Hu *et al.*, 2017a).

3. Conclusions

The recent research avenues has investigated various new solvents, in order to identify the absorbent with the lowest energy consumption for regeneration and which would eliminate the difficulties encountered for amine-based CO₂ removal systems. Among them, aqueous solutions of alkaline salt of amino acids can offer a promising alternative. In general, amino acid salt solutions can be characterized by greater stability to oxidative degradation, a good level of biodegradability, low toxicity, water-like viscosities. Although amino acids (salts) are found in a number of industrial applications, information about these systems is quite limited. Based on the study, potassium salts of Sarcosine, Lysine, and Proline can to be considered as attractive candidates for CO₂ absorption. On the other hand, it is possible that one of the amino acids already researched has the potential to absorb carbon dioxide in a new solvent configuration. For future work, the performance of an amino acid potassium salt as promoters in potassium carbonate solvents, for industrial CO₂ capture will be evaluated.

REFERENCES

- Adeosun A., Abu-Zahra M.R.M., *Evaluation of amine-blend solvent systems for CO₂ post-combustion capture applications*, Energy Procedia, **37**, 211-218 (2013).
- Aghaie M., Rezaei N., Zendejboudi S., *A systematic review on CO₂ capture with ionic liquids: Current status and future prospects*, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, **96**, 502-525 (2018).
- Ahmed R.E., Wiheeb A.D., *Enhancement of carbon dioxide absorption into aqueous potassium carbonate by adding amino acid salts*, Materials Today: Proceedings, **20**, 611–616, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.09.198> (2020).
- Ansaloni L., Hartono A., Awais M., Knuutila H.K., Deng L., *CO₂ capture using highly viscous amine blends in non-porous membrane contactors*, Chemical Engineering Journal, **359**, 1581-1591, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.11.014> (2019).
- Aronu U.E., Hartono A., Hoff K.A., Svendsen H.F., *Kinetics of carbon dioxide absorption into aqueous amino acid salt: Potassium salt of sarcosine solution*, Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research, **50**(18), 10465-10475 (2019).
- Ayoub M., Mahmood S.M., Ahmad W., Ullah S., Ahmad M., Zafar M., Farrukh S., Nasr N.H., *Carbon Dioxide CO₂ Capture Using Amino Acid Salt Solution*, Journal of Physics: Conference Series, **1123** (1) (2018).
- Bai L., Shang D., Li M., Dai Z., Deng L., Zhang X., *CO₂ absorption with ionic liquids at elevated temperatures*, Journal of Energy Chemistry, **26** (5), 1001-1006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2017.07.009> (2017).
- Bao Z., Li Q., Akhmedov N. G., Li B. A., Xing M., Wang J., Morsi B.I., Li B., *Innovative cycling reaction mechanisms of CO₂ absorption in amino acid salt solvents*, Chemical Eng. Journal Advances, **10**, 100250, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.100250> (2022).
- Behr P., Maun A., Deutgen K., Tunnat A., Oeljeklaus G., Görner K., *Kinetic study on promoted potassium carbonate solutions for CO₂ capture from flue gas*, Energy Procedia, **4**, 85-92, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.01.027> (2011).
- Borhani T.N.G., Azarpour A., Akbari V., Wan Alwi S.R., Manan Z.A., *CO₂ capture with potassium carbonate solutions: A state-of-the-art review*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **41**, 142-162 (2015).
- Brennecke J.F., Gurkan B.E., *Ionic liquids for CO₂ capture and emission reduction*, Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters, **1** (24), 3459-3464 (2010).
- Chen H., Tsai T.C., Tan C.S., *CO₂ capture using amino acid sodium salt mixed with alkanolamines*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **79**, 127-133 (2018).
- Chen P.C., Yang M.W., Wei C.H., Lin S.Z., *Selection of blended amine for CO₂ capture in a packed bed scrubber using the Taguchi method*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **45**, 245-252 (2016).
- Ciftja A.F., Hartono A., Svendsen H.F., *Amine neutralized amino acid as CO₂ absorbents: A quantitative ¹³C-NMR study*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **27**, 169-177 (2014).
- Cullinane J.T., Rochelle G.T., *Kinetics of carbon dioxide absorption into aqueous potassium carbonate and piperazine*, Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research, **45** (8), 2531-2545 (2006).

- Devries N. P., *CO₂ Absorption into Concentrated Carbonate solutions with promoters at elevated temperatures*, Environmental Regulation, on line at: https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/bitstream/handle/2142/49579/Nicholas_Devries.pdf?sequence=1 (2014).
- de Coninck H., Revi A., Babiker M., Bertoldi P., Buckeridge M., Cartwright A., Hourcade J.-C., *Strengthening and implementing the global response*, Global Warming of 1.5 C an IPCC Special Report (2018).
- Du Y., Yuan Y., Rochelle G.T., *Capacity and absorption rate of tertiary and hindered amines blended with piperazine for CO₂ capture*, Chemical Engineering Science, **155**, 397-404 (2016).
- Edenhofer O., Madrugá R. P., Sokona Y., Seyboth K., Matschoss P., Kadner S., von Stechow C., *Renewable energy sources and climate change mitigation: Special report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change*. Renewable Energy Sources and Climate Change Mitigation: Special Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2011, 1-1075, Cambridge University Press, <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139151153>.
- Farsi M., Soroush E., *CO₂ absorption by ionic liquids and deep eutectic solvents*, Advances in Carbon Capture, Methods, Technologies and Applications, chapter 4, 2020, 89-105, Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-819657-1.00004-9>.
- Godin J., Liu W., Ren S., Xu C.C., *Advances in recovery and utilization of carbon dioxide: A brief review*, Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering, **9**(4), 105644 (2021).
- Grimekis D., Giannoulidis S., Manou K., Panopoulos K.D., Karellas S., *Experimental investigation of CO₂ solubility and its absorption rate into promoted aqueous potassium carbonate solutions at elevated temperatures*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **81**, 83-92 (2019).
- Haider M.B., Hussain Z., Kumar R., *CO₂ absorption and kinetic study in ionic liquid amine blends*, Journal of Molecular Liquids, **224**, 1025-1031 (2016).
- Hallenbeck A.P., Egbeki A., Resnik K.P., Hopkinson D., Anna S.L., Kitchin J.R., *Comparative microfluidic screening of amino acid salt solutions for post-combustion CO₂ capture*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **43**, 189-197 (2015).
- Harja M., Tataru-Farnus R., Hultuana E.D., de Castro C.G., Ciobanu G., Lazar L., *Influence of ethylenediamine content over performance of CO₂ absorption into potassium carbonate solutions*, Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, **20**(4), 507-516 (2021).
- Hasib-ur-Rahman M., Siaj M., Larachi F., *Ionic liquids for CO₂ capture-Development and progress*, Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification, **49**(4), 313-322 (2010).
- Hoegh-Guldberg O., Jacob D., Taylor M., *Impacts of 1.5 C of Global Warming on Natural and Human Systems*, In Special Report, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change 175-181, online at: http://report.ipcc.ch/sr15/pdf/sr15_chapter3.pdf, (2018).
- Holst J. van, Versteeg G.F., Brilman D.W.F., Hogendoorn J.A., *Kinetic study of CO₂ with various amino acid salts in aqueous solution*, Chemical Engineering Science, **64**(1), 59-68 (2009).

- Holst J. Van, Niederer J.P.M., Versteeg G. F., Science F., *CO₂ capture from flue gas using amino acid salt solution*, *Carbon*, **31**(5), 1-6 (2012).
- Hu G., Nicholas N.J., Smith K.H., Mumford K.A., Kentish S.E., Stevens G.W., *Carbon dioxide absorption into promoted potassium carbonate solutions: A review*, *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, **53**, 28-40 (2016).
- Hu G., Smith K.H., Wu Y., Kentish S.E., Stevens G.W., *Screening Amino Acid Salts as Rate Promoters in Potassium Carbonate Solvent for Carbon Dioxide Absorption*, *Energy and Fuels*, **31**(4), 4280-4286 (2017a).
- Hu G., Smith K., Wu Y., Kentish S., Stevens G., *Recent Progress on the Performance of Different Rate Promoters in Potassium Carbonate Solvents for CO₂ Capture*, *Energy Procedia*, **114**, 2279-2286, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1374> (2017b).
- Hu G., Smith K.H., Wu Y., Mumford K.A., Kentish S.E., Stevens G.W., *Carbon dioxide capture by solvent absorption using amino acids: A review*, *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering*, **26**(11), 2229-2237, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjche.2018.08.003> (2018).
- Janiczek P., Kalb R., Thonhauser G., Gamse T., *Carbon dioxide absorption in a technical-scale-plant utilizing an imidazolium based ionic liquid*, *Separation and Purification Technology*, **97**, 20-25, [10.1016/j.seppur.2012.03.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2012.03.003) (2012).
- Jilvero H., Normann F., Andersson K., Johnsson F., *The rate of CO₂ absorption in ammonia-implications on absorber design*, *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research*, **53**(16), 6750-6758, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie403346a> (2014).
- Kasturi A., Gabitto J.F., Custelcean R., Tsouris C., *A process intensification approach for CO₂ absorption using amino acid solutions and a guanidine compound*, *Energies*, **14**(18), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14185821> (2021).
- Knuutila H., Aronu U.E., Kvamsdal H.M., Chikukwa A., *Post combustion CO₂ capture with an amino acid salt*, *Energy Procedia*, **4**, 1550-1557 (2011).
- Koronaki I.P., Prentza L., Papaefthimiou V., *Modeling of CO₂ capture via chemical absorption processes - An extensive literature review*, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, **50**, 547-566 (2015).
- Kozak F., Petig A., Morris E., Rhudy R., Thimsen D., *Chilled ammonia process for CO₂ capture*, *Energy Procedia*, **1**(1), 1419-1426 (2009).
- Kumar P.S., Hogendoorn J.A., Versteeg G.F., Feron P.H.M., *Kinetics of the reaction of CO₂ with aqueous potassium salt of taurine and glycine*, *AIChE Journal*, **49**(1), 203-213 (2003).
- Lang P., Denes F., Hegely L., *Comparison of different amine solvents for the absorption of CO₂*, *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, **61**(2016), 1105-1110 (2017).
- Lawal M.W.A., Stephenson P., Sidders J., Ramshaw C., Yeung H., *Post-combustion CO₂ Capture with Chemical Absorption: A State-of-the-art Review*, *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, **89**(9), 1609-1624 (2011).
- Lerche B.M., Stenby E.H., Thomsen K., *CO₂ Capture from Flue Gas using Amino Acid Salt Solutions*, *Energy solutions for CO₂ emission peak and subsequent decline*, *Proceedings 2009* (233-241). Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Risø Nationallaboratoriet for Bæredygtig Energi, https://www.risoe.dtu.dk/Knowledge_base/publications/Reports/ris-r-1712.aspx.
- Leung D.Y.C., Caramanna G., Maroto-Valer M.M., *An overview of current status of*

- carbon dioxide capture and storage technologies*, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, **39**, 426-443 (2014).
- Li L., Rochelle G., *Amino acid solvents for CO₂ absorption*, Separations Division - Core Programming Topic at the 2011 AIChE Annual Meeting, **1**, 8-10 (2011).
- Li Y., Wang L., Tan Z., Zhang Z., Hu X., *Experimental studies on carbon dioxide absorption using potassium carbonate solutions with amino acid salts*, Separation and Purification Technology, **219** (February), 47-54 (2019).
- Lim J.A., Kim D.H., Yoon Y., Jeong S.K., Park K.T., Nam S.C., *Absorption of CO₂ into aqueous potassium salt solutions of l-alanine and l-proline*, Energy and Fuels, **26**(6), 3910-3918 (2012).
- Liu J., Wang S., Zhao B., Tong H., Chen C., *Absorption of carbon dioxide in aqueous ammonia*, Energy Procedia, **1**(1), 933-940 (2009).
- Luo X., Liu S., Gao H., Liao H., Zhang H., Liang Z., *An Improved Fast Screening Method for Blended Amine-based Solvents for Post-Combustion CO₂ Capture*, Energy Procedia, **114** (November 2016), 1848-1854 (2017).
- Majchrowicz M.E., *Amino Acid Salt Solutions for Carbon Dioxide Capture (PhD Thesis from University of Twente)*, 2014.
- Majchrowicz M., Niederer J.P.M., Velders A.H., Versteeg G.F., *Precipitation in amino acid salt CO₂ absorption systems*, 8th International Conference on Greenhouse Gas Control (GHGT-8), 19-20 (2006).
- Molina C.T., Bouallou C., *Carbon dioxide absorption by ammonia intensified with membrane contactors*, Chemical Engineering Transactions, **45**, 253-258, <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1545043> (2015).
- Molina C.T., Bouallou C., *Comparison of Different CO₂ Recovery Processes in their Optimum Operating Conditions from a Pulverized Coal Power Plant*, Energy Procedia, **114** (November 2016), 1360-1365 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1257>.
- Mondal M.K., Balsora H.K., Varshney P., *Progress and trends in CO₂ capture / separation technologies : A review*, Energy, **46**, 431-441 (2012).
- Nwaoha C., Tontiwachwuthikul P., Benamor A., *CO₂ capture from lime kiln using AMP-DA2MP amine solvent blend: A pilot plant study*, Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering, **6**(6), 7102-7110 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2018.11.007>.
- Ochedi F., Yu J., Yu H., Liu Y., *Carbon dioxide capture using liquid absorption methods: a review*, Environmental Chemistry Letters, 10.1007/s10311-020-01093-8, (2020).
- Pacheco M.A., Kaganoi S., Rochelle G.T., *CO₂ absorption into aqueous mixtures of diglycolamine(R) and methyldiethanolamine*, Chemical Engineering Science, **55**(21), 5125-5140, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509\(00\)00104-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00104-4) (2000).
- Paul S., Thomsen K., *Kinetics of absorption of carbon dioxide into aqueous potassium salt of proline*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **8**, 169-179, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2012.02.013> (2012).
- Perinu C., Bernhardsen I.M., Svendsen H.F., Jens K.J., *CO₂ Capture by Aqueous 3-(Methylamino)propylamine in Blend with Tertiary Amines: An NMR Analysis*, Energy Procedia, **114**(1876), 1949-1955 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1326>.
- Rahman F.A., Aziz M.M.A., Saidur R., Bakar W.A.W.A., Hainin M.R., Putrajaya R.,

- Hassan N. A., *Pollution to solution: Capture and sequestration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and its utilization as a renewable energy source for a sustainable future*. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. Elsevier Ltd. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.011>.
- Ramazani R., Mazinani S., Jahanmiri A., Van der Bruggen B., *Experimental investigation of the effect of addition of different activators to aqueous solution of potassium carbonate: Absorption rate and solubility*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **45**, 27–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2015.12.003> (2016).
- Ramdin M., De Loos T.W., Vlugt T.J.H., *State-of-the-art of CO₂ capture with ionic liquids*, Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research, **51**(24), 8149-8177, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie3003705> (2012).
- Ramezani R., Mazinani S., Di Felice R., *Experimental study of CO₂ absorption in potassium Carbonate solution promoted by Triethylenetetramine*, The Open Chemical Engineering Journal, **12**(1), 67-79 (2018).
- Ramezani R., Mazinani S., Di Felice R., *State-of-the-art of CO₂ capture with amino acid salt solutions*, Reviews in Chemical Engineering, 385-392, <https://doi.org/10.1515/revce-2020-0012> (2020).
- Rivera-Tinoco R., Bouallou C., *Comparison of absorption rates and absorption capacity of ammonia solvents with MEA and MDEA aqueous blends for CO₂ capture*, Journal of Cleaner Production, **18**(9), 875-880 (2010).
- Sanchez-Fernandez E., De Miguel Mercader F., Misiak K., Van Der Ham L., Linders M., Goetheer E., *New process concepts for CO₂ capture based on precipitating amino acids*, Energy Procedia, **37**, 1160-1171 (2013).
- Sánchez L.M.G., *Functionalized Ionic Liquids Absorption Solvents for Carbon Dioxide and Olefin Separation*, In Technology (Issue 2008), Technische Universiteit Eindhoven, <https://doi.org/10.6100/IR639177>.
- Sang Sefidi V., Luis P., *Advanced Amino Acid-Based Technologies for CO₂ Capture: A Review*, Ind. and Eng. Chemistry Research, **58**(44), 20181-20194 (2019).
- Shen S., Feng X., Zhao R., Ghosh U.K., Chen A., *Kinetic study of carbon dioxide absorption with aqueous potassium carbonate promoted by arginine*, Chemical Engineering Journal, **222**, 478–487 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2013.02.093>, (2013).
- Shen S., Yang Y. Nan, Wang Y., Ren S., Han J., Chen A., *CO₂ absorption into aqueous potassium salts of lysine and proline: Density, viscosity and solubility of CO₂*, Fluid Phase Equilibria, **399**, 40-49 (2015).
- SINTEF, *Evaluation of novel post-combustion CO₂ capture solvent concepts*, Global Carbon Capture and Storage Institute, 2009, <http://www.globalccsinstitute.com/publications/evaluation-novel-post-combustion-co2-capture-solvent-concepts>.
- Sistla Y.S., Khanna A., *CO₂ absorption studies in amino acid-anion based ionic liquids*, Chemical Engineering Journal, **273**, 268-276 (2015).
- Skurygin E.F., Poroyko T.A., *Absorption of carbon dioxide with hot potassium carbonate solution: Modeling and statistical analysis of known experimental data*, Chemical Engineering Transactions, **81**, 847-852 (2020).
- Song H.J., Park S., Kim H., Gaur A., Park J.W., Lee S.J., *Carbon dioxide absorption characteristics of aqueous amino acid salt solutions*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **11**, 64-72 (2012).
- Tang Z.G., Fei W., Oli Y., *CO₂ capture by improved hot potash process*, Energy Procedia,

- 4, 307-317, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.01.056> (2011).
- Tataru- Farmus R.E., Siminiceanu I., Bouallou Ch., *Carbon dioxide absorption into new formulated amine solutions (I)*, Chemical Engineering Transactions, **12**, 175-181 (2007).
- Thee H., *Reactive absorption of carbon dioxide into promoted potassium carbonate solvents*, PhD. Thesis. August, 2013, 115, <http://hdl.handle.net/11343/38619>.
- Thee H., Nicholas N. J., Smith K. H., da Silva G., Kentish S. E., Stevens G. W., *A kinetic study of CO₂ capture with potassium carbonate solutions promoted with various amino acids: Glycine, sarcosine and proline*. International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **20**, 2120-2222, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2013.10.027> (2014).
- Tschakert P., Waisman H., Abdul Halim S., Antwi-Agyei P., Dasgupta P., Hayward B., Suarez A., *Chapter 5: Sustainable Development, Poverty Eradication and Reducing Inequalities in: Global Warming of 1.5°C*, An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global gre. IPCC SPECIAL REPORT Global Warming of 1.5°C, 445-538 (2018), https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/sites/2/2019/05/SR15_Chapter5_Low_Res.pdf
- Valenti G., Bonalumi D., *Chemical Absorption by Aqueous Solution of Ammonia*. Carbon Capture, Utilization and Sequestration, Edited by Ramesh K. Agarwal, chapter 7, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.78545> (2018).
- Wang Y., Zhao L., Otto A., Robinius M., Stolten D., *A Review of Post-combustion CO₂ Capture Technologies from Coal-fired Power Plants*, Energy Procedia, **114** (November 2016), 650-665, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1209> (2017).
- Wappel D., Gronald G., Kalb R., Draxler J., *Ionic liquids for post-combustion CO₂ absorption*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **4**(3), 486-494, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2009.11.012> (2010).
- Wu Y., Xu J., Mumford K., Stevens G. W., Fei W., Wang Y., *Recent advances in carbon dioxide capture and utilization with amines and ionic liquids*, Green Chemical Engineering, **1**(1), 16-32, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gce.2020.09.005> (2020).
- Xiao M., Liu H., Gao H., Olson W., Liang Z., *CO₂ capture with hybrid absorbents of low viscosity imidazolium-based ionic liquids and amine*, Applied Energy, **235**(October 2018), 311-319, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.103> (2019).
- Yeh J.T., Resnik K.P., Rygle K., Pennline H.W., *Semi-batch absorption and regeneration studies for CO₂ capture by aqueous ammonia*, Fuel Processing Technology, **86** (14-15), 1533-1546, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2005.01.015> (2005).
- Zarei A., Hafizi A., Rahimpour M. R., Raeissi S., *Carbon dioxide absorption into aqueous potassium salt solutions of glutamine amino acid*, Journal of Molecular Liquids, **301**, ISSN 0167-7322, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2019.111743> (2020).
- Zareie-kordshouli F., Lashani-zadehgan A., Darvishi P., *Comparative evaluation of CO₂ capture from flue gas by [Emim][Ac] ionic liquid, aqueous potassium carbonate (without activator) and MEA solutions in a packed column*, International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control, **52**, 305-318 (2016).
- Zhang C., *Absorption principle and techno-economic analysis of CO₂ absorption*

- technologies: A review*, IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci. **657** 012045 (2021).
- Zhang Y., Ji X., Xie Y., Lu X, *Screening of conventional ionic liquids for carbon dioxide capture and separation*, Applied Energy, **162**, 1160-1170, ISSN 0306-2619 (2016).
- Zhang Z., Li Y., Zhang W., Wang J., Soltanian M.R., Olabi A.G., *Effectiveness of amino acid salt solutions in capturing CO₂: A review*, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, **98**, 179-188, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.09.019> (2018).

EVALUAREA SOLVENȚILOR PE BAZĂ DE AMINOACIZI PENTRU ABSORBȚIA DIOXIDULUI DE CARBON

(Rezumat)

Separarea post-combustie și captarea CO₂ din gazele de ardere rezultate din arderea combustibililor fosili este o tehnică dificilă din cauza presiunii scăzute și a concentrației scăzute în dioxid de carbon, a impurităților din gazele de ardere și a costului. Cercetătorii au dezvoltat diverse tehnologii de captare a CO₂, cum ar fi criogenia, adsorbție, absorbția și separare prin membrană. Dintre acestea, absorbția este cea mai utilizată. O mare varietate de substanțe organice și anorganice au fost propuse ca solvenți pentru absorbția CO₂. Însă, acești solvenți au unele dezavantaje majore, cum ar fi: viteza scăzută de absorbție pentru soluțiile de K₂CO₃, consum mare de energie pentru soluțiile de amine, volatilitatea și toxicitatea ridicate în cazul soluțiilor de amoniac. Acestea pot fi rezolvate folosind un alt solvent selectiv pentru dioxid de carbon. Această lucrare oferă informații disponibile în literatura de specialitate despre solvenții actuali și sărurile de aminoacizi, potențial a fi utilizate ca absorbant pentru captarea CO₂, ca solvent individual sau în amestec.